

Description of a new species from Muscat (Oman) in the species group of *Volvarina monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Descripción de una nueva especie de Mascate (Omán) del grupo de *Volvarina monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Franck BOYER¹

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:3B9BAB4B-92B2-497C-AB21-3D909E8EBA40

Recibido el 15-V-2025. Aceptado el 7-VI-2025

ABSTRACT

A new *Volvarina* species collected in shallow waters of the Muscat region (southern Gulf of Oman) is described as *V. masqatena* and considered to belong to the species group of *Volvarina monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758). The species is described on the grounds of its shell morphology and of its animal chromatism. It is compared both with the sympatric *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897) and with the allopatric populations of *V. charbarensis* and of *V. monilis* from Masirah Island (Eastern Oman) and from the Dhofar (southern Oman). The occurrence of a *V. monilis* complex is discussed, referring to a possible circum-african distribution.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie de *Volvarina*, recolectada en aguas someras de la región de Mascate (sur del Golfo de Omán), como *V. masqatena*, y se considera que pertenece al grupo de *Volvarina monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758). La especie se describe basándose en la morfología de su concha y los patrones cromáticos del animal. Se compara con la especie simpátrica *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897) y con las poblaciones alopátricas de *V. charbarensis* y *V. monilis* de la isla de Masirah (este de Omán) y de Dhofar (sur de Omán). Se discute la presencia de un complejo de *V. monilis*, haciendo referencia a una posible distribución circunafricana.

KEY WORDS: Marginellidae, *Volvarina*, sibling species, species complex, distribution, Oman.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Marginellidae, *Volvarina*, especies hermanas, complejo de especies, distribución, Omán.

INTRODUCTION

Previously believed to be very poorly diversified in Oman, the genus *Volvarina* Hinds, 1844 has been subject to several works in the recent years (BOYER, 2015a; BOYER, 2017; COSSIGNANI & LORENZ, 2018; BOYER & RENDA, 2021) and it proves to be much more diversi-

fied than expected. One of the pivotal *Volvarina* species from Oman, *V. monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758), was previously revised by BOYER (2015b), who set the status of the species, until then recognized alternatively from West African or from East African populations. In his revision of

¹ 2 quater, route de la gare, 30840 – Meynes, France, e-mail: franck.boyer7@orange.fr

the Marginellidae of Masirah, BOYER (2017) gave more information on live populations of *V. monilis* and he compared it with its syntopic sibling *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897).

During a recent field study in Muscat (southern Gulf of Oman) in November 2024, a new *Volvarina* species closely matching *V. charbarensis* and *V. monilis* was discovered and its autonomous identity was documented on the ground of semi-intensive samplings and of careful comparison with the sympatric specimens of *V. charbarensis*, both for shell morphology and for animal chromatism. The present article presents the results of this field study, the comparison of our new species with its siblings *V. monilis* and *V. charbarensis*, and it gives some insights about the *V. monilis* species group in western Indian Ocean, as well as about the apparent occurrence of a circum-african *V. monilis* complex.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens were collected by Jose Rosado, Carlos Afonso and the author, by snorkelling on bottoms from 0.5 to 8 m, most of the specimens coming from 2-4 m. The sampling methods were principally brushing on hard bottoms and pouring sediments in bags or jars, and dredging the soft grounds with hand-sieve. After the sampling parties, the specimens were observed and compared in live condition under field binocular lens, and a good number of them were pictured as colour drawings. All the pictured specimens were saved individually in small plastic vials filled with 90° neutral alcohol (ethanol), the vial being pencilled with the drawing number; the other specimens from a same station were immersed in common vial filled with ethanol.

Few specimens of these two species were collected off Muscat by the Florida University (UF) during the years 2019-2024 and they were also examined in the frame of our study. Some of the field photographs performed by the UF team were used in our comparison work and in our

iconography. Gustav Paulay (UF) also communicated the first results of COI molecular tests about these two species.

Abbreviations used:

ad: adult
juv: juvenile
L: shell length
sh: empty shell
spm: live collected specimen
COI: cytochrome c oxidase subunit I
FMNH: Florida Museum of Natural History, Gainesville, FL, USA
MHNG: Muséum d'histoire naturelle de Genève, Switzerland
UF: University of Florida, USA
CFB: collection of the author.

RESULTS

Our new *Volvarina* species is represented in our samplings from the Muscat region by 40 live collected specimens and by 4 empty shells, 5 other wet specimens were loaned for study by the Florida University. Seventeen live collected specimens and one empty shell of *V. charbarensis* from the same samplings were used for comparison, together with one live collected specimen loaned by the Florida University. Thirty field drawings of these specimens were made by the author, and six photographs of live specimens corresponding to the six UF specimens on loan were communicated by the Florida University. Specimens and shells of *V. charbarensis* and of *V. monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758) collected previously by the author in Masirah Island (eastern Oman) and in the Dhofar (southern Oman) were also used for comparison purposes in the frame this study, together with some specimens and photographs performed by the Florida University in the same places. Few other specimens from the Muscat region (10 juvenile shells or specimens, and 2 adult empty shells) belonging to this species group were considered as not identifiable, intergrading more or less between the two forms without presenting evident diagnostic features, and they were ruled out of the results.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Superfamily VOLUTOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815
Family MARGINELLIDAE J. Fleming, 1828
Genus *Volvarina* Hinds, 1844

Type species: *Marginella nitida* Hinds, 1844 [= *Volvarina mitrella* (Risso, 1826)].

Volvarina masqatena n. sp. (Figs. 1-6)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:EE939BFE-B33E-4D3A-9766-6E7A3F92BA8E

Type material: Holotype: Oman, Muscat area • 1 ad spm (Figs 1-2), Jassa Beach, 2-8 m; MHNG-MOLL-159727, ex-CFB. Paratypes • 4 ad spm and 2 juv spm, same station as the holotype, CFB.

Other material examined: Oman, Muscat region, CFB • 1 subad spm, Al Sawadi, 1-3 m • 1 ad spm, 1 subad spm, 2 juv spm, 1 ad sh, Qurum Beach, no depth • 1 ad spm, Qurum Beach, 1-2.5 m • 4 ad spm (Figs 4-6), 1 subad spm, 4 juv spm, 1 ad sh, Qurum Beach, 2-3 m • 4 ad spm, 5 juv spm, Qurum Beach, 1-4 m • 1 juv spm, 1 juv sh, Darsait, 2-8 m • 1 ad spm, 1 subad spm, Hamaril, 3-4 m • 1 ad spm, 1 subad spm, 1 ad sh, Al Bustan Beach, 3-8 m • 7 ad spm, Qantab East Cove, 3-8 m. Oman, Muscat region, FMNH • 1 ad spm, Muscat, reef slope, 10-13 m, UF 570041 • 3 ad spm, 1 subad spm, Al Fahal Island, 3-13 m, UF 570052 (Fig. 3), UF 570335, UF 574295 (Fig. 6), UF 576755.

Type locality: Jassa Beach, southeast of Muscat area, 2-8 m.

Derivato nominis: from “Masqat”, the Arabic naming of the town of Muscat, referring to the area where the species was collected.

Description: Shell (from the holotype (Figs 1-2): Fairly small and thick for the genus (L = 5.5 mm), mostly subtransparent, subcylindrical-oval slender outline, small pointed spire of about 2.7 whorls, spiral angle of about 100°, slightly bumped lenticular small protoconch of about 1 whorl, false-suture well-visible through the shell material, thick subvertical labrum, inner labial edge smooth and straight, outer labial edge slightly bended, sloping labial shoulder, fairly wide outer margin, moderately stepped, wide and shallow anal canal, four moderately oblique columellar plaits, the lower one thin, straight and rather short, the second plait much thicker and longer, making a sharp angle protruding into the aperture, the third plait long, thin and slightly bended, the fourth plait thin and shorter, parallel to the previous one, siphonal canal very shallow, unnotched. The subtransparent body whorl is whitish on its ventral side, the area of the columellar plaits and the labrum are opaque milky white, the dorsal side of the body whorl and the

spire are slightly yellowish tinted, with a chalk-white band under the suture.

Animal (Figs. 3, 6): A thin pointed lobe at each tip of the foot forehead, and a long thin tail backside of the metapodium, long and strong tentacles and siphon, black eyes on a short peduncle. Hyaline-greyish foot, head and tentacles, some clusters of packed white spots on the sides of the foot, with dispersed white spots in the intervals and fewer yellowish and orange tiny spots, more concentrated around the axis of the metapodium. Few yellowish and orange marks on the tentacles and on the head, siphon orange flecked on a yellowish ground, whitish external mantle flecked by few orange dots, a dirty-greenish area mottled of yellowish stains on the dorsal edge, with few blackish streaks, mostly concentrated on the edge of the mantle, few small and low white pustules. Internal mantle milky white, with hardly visible orange spots dispersed over a yellowish patch ranging on the upper half-part, and a blackish comb-like mark at the upper quarter of the dorsal part, the teeth of the comb pointing down.

Variability (Figs 1-6): The shell of *Volvarina masqatena* n. sp. varies from 4.8 mm to 6.00 mm in length size at the adult stage, the most usual sizes being 5.2-5.6 mm. The shell outline can be quite oval-biconical (Fig. 6) and the spire can be rather low and somewhat blunt in some cases (Figs 4-5). In some cases, the animal can present fewer or not any small yellowish spots on the foot, fewer orange small spots on the tentacles and on the foot, rarer orange tiny spots on the foot, sometimes only occurring on the metapodium (Fig. 6); in other specimens, few black flecks are occurring on the tentacles, the siphon and the foot, and one "melanistic" specimen was observed from Darsait (2-3 m) on basaltic blackish rocks, with more black flecks and streaks on the tentacles and on the foot, a long discontinuous black streak on the edge of the external mantle, and some blackish stains on the yellowish patch on the upper half-part of the internal mantle. The siphon can have only light brown packed flecks on a whitish ground, the flecks being organized in transversal series, but in other cases it is richly decorated with a dense network of packed yellow-greenish flecks, and fewer orange and black tiny spots, the black spots being mostly grouped at the base of the siphon and on its central axis. The yellowish patch on the upper half-part of the internal

mantle is always present, most often decorated with dispersed small orange spots (except in the melanistic specimen from Darsait) and with an oblique or transversal comb-like black mark, the downwards oriented teeth of the black mark being sometimes very short, thin and more numerous as usual, and they proved to be lacking in a single case, the transversal mark resulting in a simple black line.

Distribution and habitat: The species is only known for now from the Muscat region (Muscat area and Al Sawadi Islets), where it was collected only on thin layers of soft sand covering the top of rocks and limestone pavements, in places about deprived of vegetation.

Remarks: *Volvarina masqatena* looks to be very similar to *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897) (Figs 7-9), described from Charbar, on the Mekran coast of Iran, opposite side of the Gulf of Oman. *Volvarina charbarensis* was revised from Masirah Island (Boyer, 2017: 48-64) and documented from the Dhofar (unpublished data). In the Muscat region, *Volvarina charbarensis* and *V. masqatena* were collected sympatrically in two different habitats, *V. charbarensis* being found semi-buried in soft sediments of sandy plains, whereas *V. masqatena* is found in thin layers of sands spread on hard bottoms (rocks or pavements). In the Muscat region, the shells of *V. char-*

(Right page) Figures 1-12. *Volvarina* species. 1, 2: *V. masqatena* n. sp., holotype MHNG-MOLL-159727, L = 5.5 mm, Jassa Beach, Muscat area, 2-4 m, ex-CFB; 3: *V. masqatena*, live specimen, Al Fahal Island, Muscat area, 3-10 m, UF 570052; 4, 5: *V. masqatena*, L = 5.5 mm, Qurum Beach, Muscat area, 2-3 m, CFB; 6: *V. masqatena*, live specimen, Fahal Island, Muscat area, 7-11 m, UF 574295; 7, 8: *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897), L = 8.0 mm, Qurum Beach, Muscat area, 2-3 m, CFB; 9: *V. charbarensis*, live specimen, Damanyat Island, Muscat region, sand plain, 6-14 m, UF 571198; 10-11: *V. monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758), L = 10.5 mm, Roshan Cove, Mirbat, Dhofar, 3-4 m, CFB; 12: *V. monilis*, live specimen, Mirbat, Dhofar, rocks and sand, 12-18 m, UF 576300.

(Página derecha) Figuras 1-12. Especies de *Volvarina*. 1, 2: *V. masqatena* n. sp., holotipo MHNG-MOLL-159727, L = 5,5 mm, playa de Jassa, región de Mascate, 2-4 m, ex-CFB; 3: *V. masqatena*, ejemplar vivo, isla de Al Fahal, región de Mascate, 3-10 m, UF 570052; 4, 5: *V. masqatena*, L = 5,5 mm, playa de Qurum, región de Mascate, 2-3 m, CFB; 6: *V. masqatena*, ejemplar vivo, isla de Fahal, alrededores de de Mascate, 7-11 m, UF 574295; 7, 8: *V. charbarensis* (Melvill, 1897), L = 8,0 mm, playa de Qurum, región de Mascate, 2-3 m, CFB; 9: *V. charbarensis*, ejemplar vivo, isla Damanyat, región de Mascate, llanura arenosa, 6-14 m, UF 571198; 10, 11: *V. monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758), L = 10,5 mm, cala Roshan, Mirbat, Dhofar, 3-4 m, CFB; 12: *V. monilis*, ejemplar vivo, Mirbat, Dhofar, rocas y arena, 12-18 m, UF 576300.

barensis are larger and thicker than the shells of *V. masqatena* (L = 6.00-9.00 mm versus 4.80-6.00 mm), often more slender and more cylindrical, its spire is very variable, from very low and domed (Figs 7-8) to high and pointed (Fig. 9), with spire angle measured often less than 80° (Fig. 9). The aperture is about the same in the two species, the columellar plaits are thicker in *V. charbarensis* and its outer labial margin is narrower. The shell of *V. charbarensis* is milky-white, never yellowish shaded, more opaque than the shell of *V. masqatena* (Figs 7-9), and both species have the same chalk-white spiral band under the suture. The animal chromatism of *V. charbarensis* is very similar to that of *V. masqatena*, differing principally by more dispersed white spots on the foot (versus clusters of packed white spots in *V. masqatena*) and by hardly visible grey-beige marbled stains on the upper part of the internal mantle (Fig. 9), instead of a yellowish blotch with orange dots in *V. masqatena* (Figs 3, 6). In most of the specimens of *V. charbarensis*, a thin transversal black streak is occurring above these marbled stains, rarely forming a comb-like figure (Fig. 9) like occurring always in *V. masqatena*. As a result, to separate the two species on the basis of isolated features is quite difficult, the most distinctive features of *V. masqatena* looking to be its smaller shell size, the yellowish shade on its spire and on the dorsal part of its body whorl, the clusters of packed white spots on its foot, and the yellowish blotch with orange dots on the upper half-part of its internal mantle. Few intergrading empty shells are occurring, sometimes not attributable clearly to one of these two species, especially in the case of juvenile specimens or of worn shells having possibly lost the yellowish shade occurring in the live specimens of *V. masqatena*.

Volvarina masqatena is also comparable to *V. monilis* (Linnaeus, 1758), distributed in most of far-western Indian Ocean, from eastern Oman down to the Mozambique Channel. *Volvarina monilis* has been revised by BOYER (2015b: 47-

49), documented from Masirah Island (BOYER, 2017: 7, 10-12) and more recently observed by the author in the Dhofar (unpublished data). Even if clearly related to the same species group, *Volvarina monilis* differs with more evidence from its allotropic sibling *V. masqatena*, having a much larger milky-white or very light-tan opaque shell (in Masirah: L = 6.8 mm to 15 mm), thick and rounded-oval in most cases, with a low spire presenting a spire angle over 100°, a poorly contrasted whitish spiral band under the suture, a more shouldered labrum, a wider aperture and generally a less protruding second columellar plait. *Volvarina monilis* has proportionally a much larger foot than *V. masqatena*, and its animal chromatism differs mainly by a foot mottled all over by minute yellowish dots and red-brown spots and stains, and wearing about five radial clusters of packed white spots arranged at regular distance on the lateral sides (Fig. 9). Rarely, the internal mantle is visible through the shell of *V. monilis*, showing to be creamy-white with some orange-reddish spots grouped on the upper half-part, without any blackish transversal line or comb-like mark (Fig. 9). In the populations of *V. monilis* from Masirah and from the Dhofar (like in *V. charbarensis* from these places), the red-brown marks are sometimes replaced by orange marks, even recovering the whole soft parts. Like *V. charbarensis* collected in syntopy, *V. monilis* is crawling on soft bottoms in widely open spaces, never dealing with hard bottoms. Intergrading specimens between *M. monilis* and *V. charbarensis* are occurring in Masirah, not identifiable with evidence on the ground of their shell features, or sometimes even on the ground of the animal chromatism, above all in the case of full-orange animals.

Volvarina masqatena can be considered as a semi-cryptic species, not being identified at first sight on the basis of external features, but needing a careful examination of inconspicuous features of live specimens, and possibly a comparison with live specimens with the

sympatric sibling species *V. charbarensis*. Preliminary sequence data of COI (Cytochrome Oxydase 1) were obtained at the Florida Museum of Natural History (Gustav Paulay, pers. comm.) for two specimens of *V. masqatena* from the Muscat area (preliminary identification as *V. monilis*, UF 570052 pictured in Fig. 3; UF 570041, not pictured) and for a specimen of *V. charbarensis* from the Muscat region (UF 571198 pictured in Fig. 9). The distance between these two forms in the Neighbour-Joining tree obtained from COI sequences was in the order of 0.03, considered as being already in the range of interspecific distances. COI comparison was also made with three specimens of *V. monilis* (one specimen from Mirbat, Dhofar: UF

576300 pictured in Fig. 12; two specimens from Masirah: UF 584948 and UF 585128, not pictured). The COI distance between *V. monilis* and *V. masqatena* proves to be similar (0.03) to the distance between *V. masqatena* and *V. charbarensis*. These two species share a fairly cylindrical or oval-cylindrical shell, same kind of conspicuous chalk-white subsutural bands, mostly white spotted foot, and a transversal black mark on the dorsal upper part of the internal mantle. However, COI distance is just giving a rough indication of the phyletic relationship, and further molecular tests applied to other mitochondrial and nuclear genes will contribute to give a clearer idea of the degree of relationship occurring between these three species.

DISCUSSION

Volvarina charbarensis and our new *Volvarina masqatena* were collected sympatrically in several stations of the Muscat region, mostly in the surrounds of Muscat City (Muscat area) but also in Al Sawadi Islets, on the Batinah Coast, 70 km west of Muscat. Our new species proved to be fairly common in thin layers of soft sands on the top of rocks or on limestone pavements, whereas *V. charbarensis* was only found in sandy stretches of soft or rough sediments and it proved to be much less common in term of density.

The discovery of *V. masqatena* suggests that other cryptic or semi-cryptic species may occur in the *V. monilis* species group, especially within the form *V. monilis* itself, so widely distributed from Masirah Island down to the Comores and to western Madagascar (despite being very elusive in these two areas), as well as in the whole Red Sea (the species being also fairly elusive in the northern part). The variability of *V. monilis* and of *V. charbarensis* deserves to be documented in a deeper way, and the author intends to focus on the question of the species limits within the *V. monilis* species group, on the occasion of further expeditions planned to Masirah Island, Dhofar Province and northern Red Sea.

The few specimens attributable to *V. monilis* known from the Comores Archipelago and from Western Madagascar (CFB) have a very small thick shell (7-8 mm) and a fairly cylindrical outline, like occurring in the populations from Somalia and from the type locality of the so-said junior synonym *V. terveriana* (Petit de la Saussaye, 1851) in Socotra Island, but also sometimes in Masirah Island and in the Dhofar. Another form closely matching *V. monilis* was recently described from shallow waters of Toliara, southwest of Madagascar, as *V. mangilyana* Bozzetti, 2018: the yellowish-tan light oval shells are sizing 10-12 mm, and they belong to the variability range of *V. monilis* observed from Masirah Island. Another species closely matching *V. monilis* is *V. anjathellae* Cossignani & Lorenz, 2018, simultaneously described from the Dhofar, and apparently indiscernible from *V. mangilyana* (with the same shell morphology, a size of 10-13 mm and a slightly lighter yellowish-cream shell surface) and from some specimens observed in Masirah. *Volvarina mangilyana* and *V. anjathellae* must be checked more deeply, especially concerning their animal chromatism, their radula, and possibly their molecular features, in view to verify if they

are really corresponding to autonomized species or if they just belong to the variability of *V. monilis*.

Similar forms ranging off West Africa seem to be closely related to the *V. monilis* and they are proposed to belong to a *V. monilis* complex distributed from Western Africa to Western Indian Ocean. *Volvarina sowerbyana* (Petit de la Saus-saye, 1851), collected on soft bottoms in rather shallow waters (mostly in 2-10 m) from central Senegal (Dakar) to Guinea (Conakry), has been often reported as "*V. monilis*" by authors. Its rounded-biconical shell is fairly matching some shells of *V. monilis* from Masirah islands, but many shells of *V. sowerbyana* have a light tan colour ground with three light brown spiral bands, often darker just under the suture, other shells showing just a golden shade on the dorsum, or being fully milky-white shaded. The foot of *V. sowerbyana* shows few large lateral deep-white blotches on a hyaline ground densely flecked by reddish-brown and yellowish-orange spots, the head and the tentacles wearing also reddish-brown and yellowish-orange spots. Very similar shells, mostly smaller but possibly conspecific, are known from Ivory Coast and from Ghana (CFB), presenting apparently the same animal chromatism of big white lateral blotches on a flecked ground (Peter Ryall pers. comm.).

Volvarina mariateresae (Cossignani, 2009), described from Cameroon and reported also from Gabon (Cédric Simbille pers. comm.) has a more club-shaped shell but it seems to belong to the same *V. monilis* complex, like *V. insulana* Gofas & Fernandes, 1988, described from São Tomé and presenting a more slender subcylindrical shell. These two species present a fairly similar flecked animal chromatism, *V. mariateresae* having however diffuse white clouds on the

lateral sides of the foot and yellowish spots on the tentacles (Cédric Simbille pers. comm.), both apparently lacking in *V. insulana*. *Volvarina mariateresae* has been redescribed one year later as *V. kri-biensis* Cossignani & Prella, 2010, also from Cameroon. *Volvarina walvisiana* (Tomlin, 1920), described from Walvis Bay, Namibia, and *Volvarina capensis* (Krauss, 1848) described from South Africa, seem to be related to the same species complex. The animal of *V. walvisiana* is unknown, but the animal of *V. capensis* is well-documented in the grey literature, showing deep white spots and blotches on a foot more or less flecked of reddish-orange tiny spots, a deep-white siphon stained by small reddish-orange streaks, the head and the tentacles spotted of white and reddish-orange dots, the external mantle exhibiting three large deep-white blotches on each lateral side, on a flecked ground of white, orange and blackish-brown dots.

No evident relatives belonging to this proposed *V. monilis* complex are reported for now from Angola (GOFAS & FERNANDES, 1992) and from Mozambique (Jose Rosado pers. comm.).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am indebted to Jose Rosado (Maputo, Mozambique) and to Carlos Afonso (Faro, Portugal) for their help in the field, and to Gustav Paulay (Florida University) for the photos of live specimens and the information about COI sequences. Thanks are due also to Walter Renda (Amantea, Italy) for the photos of the shells and for the mounting of the plate. Finally, I am very grateful to Serge Gofas (Malaga University) for his review of the manuscript and for his sagacious suggestions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

BOYER F. 2015a. Sur quelques *Volvarina* (Marginellidae) de l'Océan Indien Occidental. *Xenophora Taxonomy*, 6: 19-31.

BOYER F. 2015b. Révision des marginelles de Linné (Mollusques prosobranches: Marginellidae & Cystiscidae). *Xenophora Taxonomy*, 8: 33-55.

BOYER: Description of a new *Volvarina* species from Muscat (Oman)

- BOYER F. 2017. Révision des Marginellidae du récifal supérieur de l'île de Masirah (Oman). *Xenophora Taxonomy*, 17: 3-31.
- BOYER F. & RENDA W. 2021. About *Volvarina eumorpha* (Melvill, 1906) (Marginellidae) and closely related species, with description of a new species from the Gulf of Oman. *Journal of Conchology*, 44 (2): 189-197.
- COSSIGNANI T. & LORENZ F. 2018. Dieci nuove marginelle da Oman. *Malacologia Mostra Mondiale*, 100: 30-39.
- GOFAS S. & FERNANDES F. 1992. The Marginellidae of Angola. The genus *Volvarina*. *Journal of Conchology*, 34 (4): 187-198.